

Accord University

Knowledge & Vision

The impact of banking innovations on financial performance in Mogadishu, Somalia.

This proposal is submitted as partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Master of Finance and Economic development from Accord University - Somalia.

Master of Finance and Economic development

Department of Humanities

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DECLARATION PAGE

I am Juweria Abdullahi Mohamed, hereby declare that this submission is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and it contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which has been accepted for the award of any other second degree or first degree of the university or other institute of higher learning, except where due acknowledge has been made in the text and reference list.

This is to certify that this thesis is the confide work of (Juweria Abdullahi Mohamed), carried out under my supervision.

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share.

Rapidly changing customer expectations, increasing regulation and ever-greater competition from financial technology companies and other new entrants make traditional banking today a much less comfortable activity than in times past. With margins shrinking and economic uncertainty increasing, bankers recognize the need for a more agile, digital, connected and entrepreneurial operational and business environment. Innovation is no longer optional, but has become a necessity, fundamental to the success of traditional banks. Bankers need to approach innovation more systematically, driving innovation across their organizations, culture and processes. This executive report highlights key innovation lessons from the world's the most successful organizations and identifies specific strategies that can help banks innovate and outperform (IBM, n).

The modern economic science treats the concept "innovations" (innovations) as "the resulting effect of innovative activities which has received the embodiment in the form of the new or advanced product implemented in the market, the new or advanced engineering procedure used in practical activities, or in new approach to social services". Innovative activities are a complex of scientific, technological, organizational, financial and commercial actions directed to commercialization of the accumulated knowledge, technologies and the equipment. New or additional goods services or goods services with new qualities are result of innovative activities. Also, innovative activities can be determined as activities for creation, development, distribution and use of innovations.

Currently the bank sector plays an important role in the provision of innovative developments of the country economy. The solution of the task demands its competitiveness and innovative orientation of all financial-credit the economy in making financial support of a market infrastructure. Revolutionary changes in financial-credit sphere taking place in Azerbaijan Republic for the last decade caused high level dynamism of financial markets, specially of bank products market. During the short-term period of its development there was observed distribution of markets share among its participants, appearance of great amount of new participants, regular changes in the sphere of regulation market interrelationship by the government that served regular difference in additional inducements for fulfillment and change of existing Spector of bank products. These processes integrally bring us to the bank activity sphere, having the "innovative" denomination.

In relation to article subject, creation of the banking product possessing more attractive consumer properties in comparison with offered earlier, or qualitatively new product capable to satisfy needs

of his potential buyer not covered earlier, or use of more perfect technology of creation of the same banking product means.

1.1 Background

This section provides evidence and conditions of the existing situations highlighting the gap(s) to make the reader feel the urgency of the problem and equip the readers the necessary information for further understanding of the topic. According to our standard the background will define as historical background

The banking industry is continually changing, new technology is constantly being incorporated into banking systems, and industry leaders are still putting forward-thinking financial products and services. Through crowdsourcing, pilots, collaborations, and partnering, strategic investment has been made in banking innovations to create ground-breaking financial solutions. New regulations and updated banking standards have been produced as a result of the banking industry's constant change. The greatest significant change to the financial sector in recent years may be the move toward digital-only banking.

One outcome of EU law known as the second Payment Services Directive is enabling a client to obtain comprehensive banking services in real time through any channel they want (PSD2). Customers have the ability to access their accounts whenever and from any location they choose, whether it is from an online terminal at a bank branch, an ATM, a voice call, or online.

Traditional banks are investing a significant amount of money to create new services and systems in order to keep up with the consumers' evolving needs. A bank that does not take these steps will swiftly fall behind in the face of competition from both traditional banks and the new fintech businesses. Institutions are also seeking for methods to streamline their own processes, increase performance, and lower overheads.

The third Somalia Economic Update (SEU), released by the World Bank, predicts that Somalia's economy will expand at a yearly rate of 3–4%. The SEU evaluates Somalia's thriving mobile money industry and offers specific recommendations on how to introduce mobile money legislation that would improve a secure system for broad financial inclusion. The report is titled "Rapid Growth in Mobile Money: Stability or Vulnerability?"

1.2 Problem Statement

Mobile banking is expected to increase the profitability of commercial banks, as mobile banking services are geared towards increasing the velocity and circulation of money in the economy and hence more profits for the banks through commission incomes as well as gradual reduction in overhead expenses (particularly, staff, marketing and IT) which translates to an improvement in banks' profitability. Mobile banking and the need to lower transaction costs are major driving factors for the mobile banking technology's adoption.

Even though the undeniable importance of financial innovation will be explaining banking performance, the impact of innovation on performance, is still misunderstood for two main reasons, first, there is inadequate understanding about the drivers of innovation and secondly innovations' impact on bank's lowly performance untested (Mabrouk rem and Mamoghli, 2010). A study by De Young, Lang and Nolle (2007) adopt an approach to the innovation performance relationship which does not take into account the antecedents to innovation inside and outside the banking organization, all of which could influence this relationship. Somali commercial banks will continue to deploy huge investments in technology based innovations and training of manpower to handle the new technologies. The relationship between the growing investments in technology will be based bank innovations and bank financial performance in Somalia needs to be studied. There is need to establish whether innovations have contributed to the financial performance of commercial banks in Somalia Lerner and Tufano (2011) the study will be found out that product and service delivery innovations contribute positively to regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), investment and gross savings growth. Finally many studies will be done to determine the factors that influence the financial performance, but none have critically analyzed effects of innovation as a critical factor in the financial performance of commercial banks in Somalia. The aim of this study will be close this gap by investigating the effects of banking innovation on financial performance of commercial banks in Mogadishu Somalia.

1.3 General Objective / Aim / Purpose

The main objective of this study is to determine the **impact of banking innovations on financial performance in Mogadishu, Somalia.**

1.4 Specific objectives

The specific objectives of this study are summarized in the below paragraph:

- ❖ To describe the impact of mobile banking on financial performance in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ❖ To find out the impact of internet banking on financial performance of in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ❖ to identify the impact of banking innovation on income in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ❖ to identify the impact of banking innovation on cost, quality, time, and flexibility in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ❖ to identify the impact of banking innovation on customer retention, attraction satisfaction in Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.5 Research Questions

The research questions of this study are summarized in the below paragraph:

- ❖ What is the impact of mobile banking on financial performance in Mogadishu, Somalia.?
- ❖ What is the impact of internet banking on financial performance of in Mogadishu, Somalia.?
- ❖ What is the impact of banking innovation on income in Mogadishu, Somalia.?
- ❖ What is the impact of banking innovation on cost, quality, time, and flexibility in Mogadishu, Somalia.?
- ❖ What is the impact of banking innovation on customer retention, attraction satisfaction in Mogadishu, Somalia?

1.6 Significance/Importance/justification

Because research serves as the foundation for nearly all government policies in our economic system, such as those of the government, this study will be important to policymakers, such as the

government of Somalia, the Central Bank of Somalia, and the Ministry of Finance, who develop financial system policies. In addition, this study will be of importance to all financial institutions, including commercial banks, microfinance institutions, and cooperative societies, since it provides insight on the role of financial institutions towards economic growth. This study will be useful for future researchers because it will act as a source of information and a guideline for them to follow in subsequent studies related to the same problem under investigation. The study will also be beneficial to institutions, both public and private, because it will raise awareness of existing issues and provide appropriate methods for developing long-term solutions to the problems under investigation. The study will also be beneficial to the local community because it creates awareness of the severity of a particular problem and the urgency of the need for a solution. The study will also be important to Islamic banks because it will determine whether Islamic banks play any role in economic growth, and its recommendations will provide additional insights into how Islamic banks can boost economic growth. Finally, the study will benefit prospective researchers and institutions because it will add to existing knowledge and may uncover additional gaps in the literature that will necessitate further investigation.

1.7. Scope of the study

- ❖ Content scope:
 - ❖ The study is about the relationship between Islamic banking and economic growth in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ❖ Geographical scope:
 - This study directly focuses on a specific group in a specific country, particularly Mogadishu residents. The content of this study was limited to Somali residents who worked in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ❖ Time scope:
 - This research will be carried out between September 2022 and January 2023. This is the time period during the University Research has allocated funds for students to conduct their studies.

1.8. Definition of KeyTerms

- ❖ Innovation consists of the generation of a new idea and its implementation into a new product, process or service, leading to the dynamic growth of the national economy and the increase of employment as well as to a creation of pure profit for the innovative business enterprise.

Innovation is never a one-time phenomenon, but a long and cumulative process of a great number of organizational decision-making processes, ranging from the phase of generation of a new idea to its implementation phase. New idea refers to the perception of a new customer need or a new way to produce. It is generated in the cumulative process of information-gathering, coupled with an ever-challenging entrepreneurial vision. Through the implementation process the new idea is developed and commercialized into a new marketable product or a new process with attendant cost reduction and increased productivity” (Urabe, 1988).

- ❖ Commercial bank is a financial institution that provides services, such as accepting deposits, giving business loans and auto loans, mortgage lending, and basic investment products like savings accounts and certificates of deposit. The traditional commercial bank is a brick and mortar institution with tellers, safe deposit boxes, vaults and ATMs. However, some commercial banks do not have any physical branches and require consumers to complete all transactions by phone or Internet. In exchange, they generally pay higher interest rates on investments and deposits, and charge lower fees (Business Dictionary, 2011).
- ❖ Commercial banks are financial intermediaries who are the main providers of credit to the household and corporate sector and operate the payments mechanism.
- ❖ “ICT” means Information and Communication Technology and refers to the combination of manufacturing and services industries that capture, transmit and display data and information electronically (michalsons, Oct 27, 2022)”
- ❖ M-Banking or m-banking. M-banking is defined as “a form of banking transaction carried out via a mobile phone”. Moreover, it is defined as a “type of execution of financial services in the course of which - within an electronic procedure- the customer uses mobile communication techniques in conjunction with mobile 3 devices”. The technologies generally used for mobile banking are Interactive Voice Response (IVR), Standalone Mobile Application Clients, Short Messaging Service (SMS) and Wireless Application Protocol (WAP)
- ❖ Income is money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing labor, producing a good or service or investing capital. Individuals typically earn income through wages or salary, while businesses earn income from selling goods or services above their cost

of production. Most forms of income are subject to taxation, which can substantially decrease the actual amount of money that an individual can keep and use at their own discretion (Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences, 2010)

- ❖ Quality is the degree to which an object or entity (e.g., process, product, or service) satisfies a specified set of attributes or requirements. The quality of something can be determined by comparing a set of inherent characteristics with a set of requirements (Enrique Diaz, 2014).
- ❖ Customer retention definition: Customer retention refers to a company's ability to turn customers into repeat buyers and prevent them from switching to a competitor. It indicates whether your product and the quality of your service please your existing customers. It's also the lifeblood of most subscription-based companies and service providers (Sarah Olson, 2020).
- ❖ Customer retention encompasses many different activities. At a basic level, customer retention looks at how long customers stay customers.
- ❖ Customer satisfaction is a metric for how well a company, product, or service fulfills the needs and expectations of a consumer.
- ❖ Mobile banking is the act of making financial transactions on a mobile device (cell phone, tablet, etc.). This activity can be as simple as a bank sending fraud or usage activity to a client's cell phone or as complex as a client paying bills or sending money abroad (Markoska, 2018).
- ❖ An automated teller machine (ATM) is an electronic banking outlet that allows customers to complete basic transactions without the aid of a branch representative or teller. Anyone with a credit card or debit card can access cash at most ATMs, either in the USA or abroad (JULIA KAGAN, 2022).
- ❖ Internet banking is a method of banking in which transactions are conducted electronically via the internet. Online banking allows a user to conduct financial transactions via the Internet.

1.9. Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction:

This chapter conducts a literature review on bank innovations. It discusses the key theories. Underlying bank innovations, develops a conceptual framework, and expounds on the research gaps on bank innovations and financial performance.

2.1 Bank innovation and financial performance.

Innovations in information, communication, and technology (ICT) have transformed the financial sector, resulting in novel delivery channels for financial products and services such as ATMs, mobile phone banking, internet banking, and agency banking (Ahmad, 2006). These ICT-enabled advancements are known as electronic banking (e-banking), which is a subset of electronic commerce (E-commerce). E-banking has played a significant role in enhancing bank service quality and financial performance (Beck et al., 2007). Branchless banking, or the use of alternate delivery channels such as mobile phone banking and agent banking, is becoming increasingly popular among Kenyan and other developing-country commercial banks. It is hoped that it would reach low-income and rural residents while also improving their quality of life.

Innovations in information, communication, and technology (ICT) have transformed the financial sector, resulting in novel delivery channels for financial products and services such as ATMs, mobile phone banking, internet banking, and agency banking (Ahmad, 2006). These ICT-enabled advancements are known as electronic banking (e-banking), which is a subset of electronic commerce (E-commerce). E-banking has played a significant role in enhancing bank service quality and financial performance (Beck et al., 2007). Branchless banking, or the use of alternate delivery channels such as mobile phone banking and agent banking, is becoming increasingly popular among Kenyan and other developing-country commercial banks. The process of calculating the monetary value of the outcomes of a company's policies and operations is known as accounting for financial results. It is used to measure a company's total financial health over the course of a certain period of time. Additionally, it can be used to compare similar enterprises operating within the same industry as well as to compare industries or sectors on an aggregate level. The balance of income-generating activities and the expense of activities associated to such activities has a significant impact on a commercial bank's capacity to turn a profit. Commercial banks have changed their behavior regarding sources of income by increasingly diversifying into non-intermediation income generating activities as opposed to the conventional intermediation income generating activities. This is because the problem of profitability and the intense competition in the industry has forced commercial banks to modify their behavior. In order to maintain their market share, commercial banks need to continually innovate and incorporate new goods and technologies into their operations. These products include the utilization of technology, such as internet banking and cell phone banking (McKay and Pickens, 2010). Islamic products are also included in this category.

DeYoung et al. (2007) conducted an in-depth investigation into the financial standing of pure-play internet banks located in the United States. According to the findings of the study, Internet-only financial institutions have relatively lower profitability than branching banks. This disparity can be partially attributed to high labor expenses, low fee-based revenues, and the difficulty in generating deposit funding. The findings, however, suggested that banks that only operate online tended to expand at a faster rate than conventional banks with branch locations. This finding is in line with the typical model for internet banking. Internet-only banks have access to deeper scale economies than branching banks do; as a result, Internet-only banks are expected to become more financially competitive over time as they grow larger. This is because Internet-only banks have access to deeper scale economies than branching banks do. The findings of Delgado et al. (2004) and Delgado et al. (2006) for Internet-only banks in the EU were comparable. Despite this, the quantity of technology-based scale savings discovered in these investigations was a significant amount greater than that expected by DeYoung studies. Kithuka (2012) conducted research with the goal of identifying the elements that are driving the expansion of agency banking in Kenya. In the course of the research, a total of one hundred Equity Bank branches in Kwale County participated in bank-focused, bank-led, and non-bank-led transactions. According to the findings of the study, the usage of agency banking is influenced by factors such as the ease of using the technology to transfer money, as well as its affordability, support, and safety. Waithanji (2012) aimed to determine the impact that agent banking has in Kenya as a means of advancing the country's financial system. In order to conduct the analysis, descriptive statistics were utilized. The data indicated that there was no connection between agent banking and the deepening of the financial system. The researcher pointed out that the association could not be definitively confirmed due to the low number of banks that had implemented it, and the researcher speculated that the impact would become clearer once all banks adopted agency banking. Kirimi (2011) conducted research to determine how far commercial banks in Kenya have progressed in implementing agency banking. According to the findings of the study, it is difficult to enforce sufficient control by the agent, and the study also found that client interaction was inconsistent with the broader regulatory framework for the banking industry. The findings showed that there is a need for regular training of agents on changes in operational processes and policies. This training is necessary to eliminate the occurrence of errors and mistakes that impede the penetration of agency banking in Kenya, which ultimately leads to an improvement in the financial performance

of banks.

2.2 Banking innovations on income stream.

Banks in India have, for a number of years now, been shifting their attention toward non-interest income streams as a means of supplementing the money they receive from the more traditional operations that earn them interest. This shift toward innovation adoption and new income streams has been more obvious for new private and foreign banks, whilst there appears to have been considerable hesitation on the part of public sector banks and established private banks. This article investigates the influence on performance (as evaluated by profitability and income stability) that Indian banks experienced as a result of shifting their focus to new sources of revenue and, as a consequence, increasing their level of diversity.

A comparison of the income that various bank groups in India generate from these different income streams reveals that new private banks and foreign banks in India have been more successful than public sector banks in generating a greater proportion of their income from non-interest and fee-based sources. This is in contrast to the public sector banks, which generate a greater proportion of their income from interest-based sources. On the other hand, in the context of India, increasing diversification cannot be related to higher risk-adjusted performance. Using multiple regression analysis, this study examines the impact that diversification and an increasing share of fee-based income have had on profitability and risk-adjusted profitability for all banks in India over the period of 2005–2012. The study focuses on the period between 2005 and 2012.

According to the findings of the paper, the increasing proportion of fee-based income and non-interest income relative to total income and diversification has a beneficial effect on profitability; however, this effect does not have a statistically significant bearing on risk-adjusted performance, and consequently, stability. However, the paper emphasizes that the impact direction of diversity measures may be negative, which is in agreement with what many studies have revealed in the contexts of the United States, Europe, Australia, and India. While the results show that diversification has a beneficial impact on profitability, the study notes that the impact direction of diversification measures may be negative.

In this article, the impact of diversity in total income is considered separately from the impact of diversification in income from sources other than interest. This diversification score is helpful in determining whether or not the banks are generating their non-interest revenue only from fee income, solely from their own investments, or whether or not they have diversified the generation

of their non-interest income by focusing on both fee income and their own investments. It is important to note that there is a positive impact of rising share of 'fee income' in both total income and non-interest income on profitability as well as risk-adjusted measures. This is the case since fee income is a non-interest source of revenue. The findings highlight that even while public sector banks need to create more income from fee-based activities, it would be vital to choose sources of fee-based income that remain stable and have a good influence on risk-adjusted measures. This is because the results highlight that public sector banks have a greater responsibility to mitigate risk than private sector banks do.

One of the most important factors that contribute to economic expansion is innovation, which the Oxford Dictionaries¹ have summed up as "a new method, idea, product, etc." According to Cohen and Levinthal (1990), innovation is a lengthy process that is vitally dependent on the recognition of new information from the outside world, integrating that information, and applying it to achieve commercial purposes. During the course of this process, it is possible that several of the new ideas will become sidetracked even while they are still in the gestation period and will be need to leave. According to Utterback and Abernathy (1975), there are consistent patterns in the factors that stimulate innovation, the many forms of innovation, and the factors that inhibit innovation, including economic barriers. According to Morris (1986), one of the economic factors that can act as a barrier to innovation is the requirement to produce the required incentives for adoption and for instability of incumbents.

2.3 Impact of banking innovations on customer attraction, satisfaction and retention

It is well acknowledged that innovation is one of the most essential factors that contribute to an organization's level of competitiveness. Research has shown beyond a shadow of a doubt that innovation is the way to both growth and economic prosperity for any country or organization (Ikeda and Marshall, 2016; Vys and Raitani, 2014). Innovation is the key to both growth and economic prosperity for any country or organization. (Akturan and Tezcan, 2012; Chiu et al., 2017; Mullan et al., 2017) The twenty first century ushered in a new era for financial institutions, which compels them to compete using various technologies in order to either serve the customers better or meet their expectations. This new era for banking institutions was ushered in by the twenty first century. According to Ayo et al. (2016), Mishra (2014), and Kamakodi and Khan (2008), the implementation of new technology by financial institutions has stimulated the development of supplementary client services and products. According to Ladeira et al. (2016) and Malinconico and Fuccio (2016), clients

of banks are looking for services that are both quicker and more efficient in order to meet and fulfill their requirements. It is important to highlight that innovations in commercial banking have completely changed the method in which customers conduct their financial transactions. According to Vyas and Raitani (2014), customers can now perform banking transactions at any time and from any location in the world without needing to be physically present at the bank counters. Because of these forward-thinking approaches, banking services are now both more effective and more convenient for customers than they have ever been before. In point of fact, it is thought that consumers understand innovation to be "an idea, practice, process, product or service that is new to an individual or other unit of adoption" (Rogers, 1983, 1995, page 11). Mobile banking, online banking, and electronic wallets are examples of innovative banking services that enable a multi-channel banking strategy by giving new ways for customers to engage with the bank (Mbama and Ezepeue, 2018). Innovative banking services occur in a variety of forms and can be categorized as service innovations. The presumption that such business practices would increase the level of consumer attraction, contentment, and retention underpins the rationale that underpins the development of innovatively driven services and products. According to the findings of several studies, the banking business is quite competitive. Not only are banks in competition with one another, but they are also in competition with other types of financial entities that are not banks (Clemes et al., 2007; Hull, 2002; Yap et al., 2012). This form of competition has not only resulted in an enhancement of the services supplied by commercial banks to their consumers, but it has also led to the introduction of services that are driven by innovation (Mbama and Ezepeue, 2018; Mullan et al., 2017). However, the product development areas of the vast majority of commercial banks are simple to replicate. Because banks provide comparable services and products, the only way to differentiate such services and products is by the prices they charge and the standards to which they adhere in providing such services and products. In a similar vein, innovation is considered to be a driving force behind commercial banking modernization due to the fact that it improves an organization's overall competitiveness (Agolla and Van Lill, 2016; Vigoda-Gadot et al., 2005). Companies that have taken an all-encompassing approach to innovation have a distinct competitive advantage in markets that are already intensely competitive. This is due to the fact that they have been successful in acquiring, retaining, and satisfying their existing consumers, which has resulted in an increase in the value of their portfolios in the market. According to Cohen et al. (2006), customer retention has the potential to be an effective weapon that banks may utilize to acquire a strategic advantage and survive in today's ever-changing banking competitive market. This is owing to

the fact that there is not much of a difference between the services that are provided by various banks. However, customer retention is not something that comes easy or cheaply in a competitive market. This is especially true when considering the fast advancing innovation landscape in the banking business as well as the varied preferences of customers regarding banking services and products (Mohit and Pooja, 2013).

According to Amin (2016) and Wonglimpiyarat (2017), technological innovation has radically transformed the commercial banking industry's business landscape. According to Mishra (2014) and Thakur (2014), the development of innovative services and products such as online banking, e-Wallet, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), Mobile banking, and many more, has altered the manner in which commercial banks attract, satisfy, and retain their customers. According to Proenca and Rodrigues (2011), technological advancements in the banking industry are becoming obsolete many of the conventional banking services, including telegraphic transfers, travelers' cheques, and bank checks. When it comes to conducting their financial dealings, customers today have access to a wide range of different possibilities. Consumers no longer need to physically present themselves at the counters of the banking hall in order to move money from one account to another, from one bank to another, or even from one nation to another (Jan and Abdullah, 2014). This makes money transfers much simpler and more convenient. According to Amin (2016) and Wu et al. (2006), the development of all of these services and products has been driven by technological advancements, competition, and an emphasis on consumer pleasure. This assumption has been empirically supported by other research (Khan, 2010; Musiime and Bayaki, 2010), which can be found here and here. Because of this, innovation shortens the amount of time it takes to complete a transaction, which in turn makes life more convenient for customers by doing things like getting rid of lines and making it possible to send money quickly.

2.4 E-Banking and its impact on Banks' performance and customers behavior.

According to Amin (2016) and Wonglimpiyarat (2017), technological advancement has fundamentally altered the way commercial banks do their operations. According to Mishra (2014) and Thakur (2014), the emergence of innovative services and products like as online banking, e-Wallets, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), Mobile Banking, and many more, has altered the manner in which commercial banks attract, satisfy, and retain their customers. According to Proenca and Rodrigues (2011), technological advancements in the banking industry are rendering traditional banking services like travelers' cheques, bank checks, and telegraphic transfers obsolete. When it

comes to conducting their financial dealings, customers today have a wide array of options at their disposal. According to Jan and Abdullah (2014), it is now simple and straightforward for customers to transfer monies from one account to another, from one bank to another, and even from one nation to another without having to physically present themselves at the counters of the banking hall. According to Amin (2016) and Wu et al. (2006), the development of all of these services and products has been primarily motivated by technological advancements, competitive pressure, and an emphasis on satisfying customers. The findings of additional research (Khan, 2010; Musiime and Bayaki, 2010) provide empirical support for this assumption. As a result, innovation shortens the amount of time needed to complete a transaction, which in turn makes life more convenient for clients by doing away with the need to stand in line and enabling faster money transfers.

2.5. Customer satisfaction impact on banking services and relationship management innovation.

Customers are unable to make an accurate assessment of services prior to the performance of the service, in contrast to the evaluation of items. According to Gil (2008), the most important factor in determining how well a service performs is the interaction that occurs between the service provider and the clients. This interaction is referred to as the "service encounter." During these interactions, the consumer has the opportunity to form an opinion regarding the manner in which the organization delivers its products and services. His or her customer service experience can be summed up by the ways in which he or she interacted with the company, its procedures, and its staff. As a result, the foundation of customer happiness is built around the interactions that occur during service. According to Wirtz (1994), service providers have a substantial amount of opportunity to manage the encounters that collectively make up the experience. They are able to create and maintain the service environment, selectively target, socialize, and educate customers; select, train, and manage service staff; design and maintain the interactive production process; and design and maintain the interactive production process. According to Manrai, L.A. and Manrai, A.K. (2007), the concept of customer satisfaction in financial services is typically conceived of as a multidimensional construct. The list of bank service features that are used for the measuring of customer satisfaction includes components such as the appearance of the facility, the attitude

and behavior of the employees, the decor and ambiance, the business hours, the interest rate, and the amount of time spent waiting. Customers of the bank might not place the same level of importance on each of these components as they do on the others.

2.6 The Effects of Technological Innovation on the Banking Sector

There have been significant shifts in the banking industry all over the world as a direct result of the substantial impact that innovations and trends in information and communication technology, business intelligence, and risk management methods have had. The fundamental problem that has to be solved is no longer adjusting to shifts in the banking industry; rather, it is figuring out how to function more effectively in the new business environment in order to rethink one's connections with one's clientele, make the most of the opportunities presented by the processes of innovation, and produce satisfactory profits. If a bank is serious about moving forward, it must remain flexible enough to continually adjust to the shifting economic, financial, and productive landscape. This article presents an argument regarding the influence that the progression and complexity of developing technologies have on the structural and behavioral factors that are meant to be financial criticalities and requirements, which restrict the strategic development alternatives available to banks. An empirical examination of quantitative and qualitative data pertaining to the years 2008–2011 that was collected from a sample of 3,190 banks situated in 17 different countries was used to validate the research assumptions. The empirical research shows that (1) there is a negative relationship between financial leverage and the two technological innovations regarding enterprise resource planning software systems and software for management of credit risk; (2) the enterprise resource planning innovation and the software for management of credit risk seem to influence the competences, abilities, and organization of the banking system; and (3) the innovations that concern the enterprise resource planning software systems and the software for the management of credit risk increase the earning margin of banks.

2.7 Impact of Innovation on Realizing Competitive Advantage in Banking Sector in Jordan on time cost flexibility

In an environment of high velocity change, short products life cycle, mass customization, and narrowing customer niches, the successful integration of technology and marketing capabilities for a given product conveys little long term strategic advantage to firms.(Fowler et al., 2000). Competitive advantage has a wide definition range, in this article; the dimensions of competitive advantages were derived from Clark, Hayes, & Wheelwright model. As they suggested that firms compete in the marketplace by virtue of one or more of the following competitive priorities. Time, quality, and cost

are, along with flexibility, the basic measurements for assessing all business activities.(Clark et al., 1988). Innovation may not be within the original dimensions of Clark, Hayes, & Wheelwright definition, however, Innovation is known as a critical factor for firms to create value and sustain competitive advantage in today's highly complex and dynamic environment (Ranjit, 2004). That being said, not many empirical studies fully explored the relationship between innovation and competitive advantage can be found especially in the banking sector. Banking industry is one of the major components of the Jordanian economy, with the total number of 25 banks: 9 international banks and 16 national Jordanian banks: 3 of which are Islamic Banks. Twenty-five Banks with more than 666 branches and 81 offices around the country, and 155 branches internationally. The majority of the branches are located in the capital city (Amman), more than 414 branches out of 666 are located in Amman. (Association of Banks in Jordan, 2011). This indicates clearly the importance and significance of this sector in Jordan is increasing, so does the competition among the banks, therefore these banks have to look for creative methods to compete, innovation: is one of the most important bases for achieving competitive advantage. Despite the extent of studies that have looked at innovation there are still clear gaps in the literature. Most notable is the need for greater understanding of the actual impact of innovation on realizing competitive advantage. Additionally, most other studies are largely focused on the experiences of developed countries. There is a paucity of research regarding innovation and competitive advantage in developing countries (including Jordan) and particularly in the banking sector. So the examination and exploration of innovation impact and competitive became the driving force behind this study. Michal Porter (1985) considered that competitive advantage grows out of value a firm is able to create for its buyers that exceeds the firm's cost of creating it. Value is what buyers are willing to pay, and superior value stems from offering lower prices than competitors for equivalent benefits or providing unique benefits that more than offset a higher price. Porter recognized competitive advantage as a strategic goal; that is a dependent variable and the reason behind this is that the good performance is related to achieving a competitive advantage (Reed &Defillippi, 1990). Clark, Hayes, and Wheelwright suggested that firms compete in the marketplace by virtue of one or more of the following competitive priorities. Time, quality, and cost are, along with flexibility. (Clark et al.,1988).Several academics and practitioners have taken these four indicators, modified or not, over the past years. Many authors and practitioners have added to and adapted this list over the years. Foo and Friedman (1992) for example proposed a set of six competitive priorities, adding service and manufacturing technology to the above while expanding time into: time to market

and lead times. Others have added innovation and dependability. The researchers found that the original concept of competitive priorities suggested by Clark, Hayes, and Wheelwright fits to analyze the impact of innovation on competitive advantage, since whether innovation was a part of the competitive advantage dimensions or not, the numerous studies, and different business and marketing schools agree on the importance of innovation to the competitive advantage of the firms. Below is a brief description of competitive advantage dimensions analyzed in this study.

2.7.1 Time

The original term lead-time used by Hayes and Wheelwright (1984) is rephrased as time in this article. It is seen as the total time an activity requires to be executed, from the very beginning to the very end. Firms can consider the time factor to compete among each other. Delivery time can be a source of competitive advantage when firms try to reduce the period of time between receiving and accepting customer orders and provisions of products or services to customers (Stonebrake & Leong, 1994). It is also a measure of the firms' adherence to delivery schedules agreed upon with customers. The speed of product development also refers to the time factor; that is the time period between product idea generation till achieving the final design or production (Evans, 1993).

2.7.2 Quality

Crosby (1995) defined quality in his concepts of the Four Absolutes of Quality and the Cost of Poor Quality as conformity to certain specifications. Juran (2004) described quality as "Fitness for use" where fitness is defined by the customer. Weinberg (1993) defines fitness more holistically as "value to some person." Quality can be achieved by adding unique attributes to products to enhance their competitive attractiveness so as to benefit customers in the final stage (Best, 1997: cited by Al-Rousan and Qawasmeh, 2009). Also, quality can be achieved through a couple of dimensions such as the quality of design which means to adapt product design to its function (Adam & Ebert, 1996), and the quality of conformity which stands for the organizational capability to transform inputs to conformable outputs (Hill, 1993) or outputs in accordance to the specific design characteristics, and the focus on quality will be reflected in competitive advantage and profitability of the organization.

2.7.3 Cost

Costs can be direct or indirect, fixed or variable, and short or long-term. Additionally, cost can also be expressed according to its intention. Further, cost of quality can be subdivided into failure, appraisal, and prevention costs (Juran, 2004). Firms must make some kind of compromise between the cost and the characteristics of their products and services. In general, most organizations choose to cut total cost

by stripping fixed costs and applying continuous control on raw materials, reducing employee compensation rates, and by achieving higher levels of productivity (Dilworth, 1992).

2.7.4 Flexibility

Knoll and Jarvenpaa (1994) described flexibility as an essential property for the maintenance of fit between Business Processes and their supporting systems in changing environments. Florian Forster defined flexibility as the ability to react to changes. (Forster, 2006). Flexibility can be viewed as the ability of the processes to switch from one product to another or from one customer to another at the least cost or impact. Flexibility also can be defined as the ability to adapt the production capacity to changes in the environment or market demands (Evans, 1993). Flexibility also encompasses product flexibility in the first place which is defined as the ability of the organization to trace changes in consumers' needs, tastes and expectations so as to carry out changes in product designs. The second flexibility has to do with volume which stands for the organization's capability to respond to changes in consumer demand. It is believed that such flexibility can yield benefits such as introducing new products along with product variety, and controlling volume and delivery time (Stake et al., 1998).

2.8 The Impact of Innovation on Banking Performance:

Many researchers have examined the relationship between innovation and banks' performance theoretically and empirically. This study provides first, the Solow Paradox theory. Second, it discusses the impact of mobile banking and investment in computer software on banks performance. And finally, it provides empirical evidence. The Solow paradox also called productivity paradox is originated by Robert Solow, a Nobel Prize winner in economics. During 1970s and 1980s, the United States (US) have witnessed a slowdown of productivity growth. The average labor productivity between 1947 and 1973 was 2.4% compared to 1% between 1973 and 1988 (Federal Reserve Bank of Richmond, 1989). This decrease in productivity was observed in spite of the huge development in Information Technology (IT) investment. Accordingly, Solow (1987), as cited by Ben Romdhane (2013), has stated during his Nobel speech that "you can see the computer age everywhere but in the productivity statistics". Thus, the investment in IT has no impact on productivity. As result, many academic researchers have failed to prove any significance between IT investment and the increase in overall productivity in US (Yosri, 1992; Weill, 1992). Significant productivity can be attributed to transactional types of IT, but there are no gains associated with strategic systems or IT investment (Weill, 1992). Many studies tried to explain the productivity paradox (Brynjolfsson, 1993). According to Brynjolfsson (1993), there are 4 categories to group the various explanations proposed: (1)

Mismeasurement of outputs and inputs, (2) Lags due to learning and adjustment, (3) Redistribution and dissipation of profits, and (4) Mismanagement of information and technology. Some other studies have resolved the productivity paradox, by proving that there is a delay between IT investment and productivity jump (Dewan and Kraemer, 1998). IT investments are productive, but their benefits are realized only after a lag period, during which complementary capital investments must be developed to allow for the use of computers to their full potential (David, 1990). Finally, many economists do not approve the existence of a productivity paradox. They view it more as a series of unwanted assumptions about the impact of IT on productivity than a paradox (David, 1990).

Mobile Banking and Financial Performance Mobile banking, as previously defined, is a form of innovation that is used to make transactions through bank application downloaded on smart phones that are transformed into pocket banks. It refers to providing financial and banking services with the help of mobile telecommunication devices. These services are performed distantly from traditional branches. As a result, mobile banking could be denoted as branchless banking. Some authors consider mobile banking as an appendage of ebanking (Abaenewe et al., 2013), while others consider it as a separate delivery channel (Mwange, 2013) Banking services that could be provided by mobile banking are in general: checking accounts balances, checking new products and services, simulating loans, monitoring transactions, locating traditional branches and ATMs, transferring funds, converting currencies, paying bills and much more services. The diversification of these services depends on the degree of banks' involvement in innovation. Many researchers have reviewed the impact of mobile banking on banks financial performance. As previously mentioned, the Solow paradox is the main theory used to explain the impact of mobile banking, and generally of IT investment, on banks productivity and performance. In many studies, Solow paradox has been rejected. According to Mwange (2013), mobile banking leads to higher financial performance through higher operational efficiency. This latter is achieved through conducting targeted marketing campaigns based on tracking customers' preferences. In consequence, bank's expenses in terms of marketing will decrease. Moreover, it is achieved through decreasing staff numbers since less face to face transactions are performed. Wishart (2006) stated that mobile banking could lead to higher customer loyalty, increased market shares and declining operational costs. According to Tiwari et al. (2006), 15% of banks customers would change their banks if it fails to provide mobile banking services in Germany. Mania (2012) has stated that mobile banking positively affect financial performance since banks could serve a larger number of customers within a shorter period of time. This positive relationship was supported

by many researchers at different significance levels (Abaenewe et al., 2013; Kithaka, 2014; Kathuo et al., 2015). Paradoxically, in line with Solow paradox, other researchers could not find any significant relationship between mobile banking and bank's financial performance (Alber, 2010; Mutua, 2013). According to Alber (2010), this insignificant relationship is attributed to 2 main reasons. First, high perceived risk in mobile banking and low confidentiality. And second, low knowledge about different services in mobile banking. Based on the previous discussion, this research considers that mobile banking positively affects banking performance.

2.9 Financial Performance of Commercial Banks

Performance measurement and reporting is now widespread across the private sector as well as public sector of many industrialized and industrializing countries (Williams, 2003). The common tool that is used for this process, key performance indicators (KPIs), have been argued to provide intelligence in the form of useful information about a public and private agency's performance (Williams, 2003). Scholars like Modell (2004), Moynihan (2005), Vakkuri and Meklin (2006) have maintained that the implementation of performance measurement systems possess important symbolic value. 34 KPIs are viewed as a good management device and a socially constructed tool that makes sense (DeKool, 2004). The fact that KPIs tend to be quantitative has helped to promote their image of objectiveness and rationality. The image of KPIs is further enhanced by their widespread application across the many sectors of many countries. The importance of performance measurement is noted by Ingraham (2005) that it is important to expect that citizens see and understand the results of organizational programs. Cicea and Hincu (2009) state that commercial banks represent the core of the credit for any national economy. In turn, the credit is the engine that put in motion the financial flows that determine growth and economic development of a nation. As a result, any efficiency in the activities of commercial banks has special implications on the entire economy. The management of every commercial bank must establish a system for assessing investment performance which suits its circumstances and needs and this evaluation must be done at consecutive intervals to ensure the achievement of the Bank's investment objectives and to know the general direction of the behavior of investment activity in the past and therefore predict the future. Profitability offers clues about the ability of the bank to undertake risks and to expand its activity. The main indicators used in the appreciation of the bank profitability are: Return on equity, ROE ($\text{Net income} / \text{Average Equity}$), Return on Asset, ROA ($\text{Net income} / \text{Total assets}$) and the indicator of financial leverage or ($\text{Equity} / \text{Total Assets}$) 35 (Dardac and Barbu, 2005). The indicators are submitted to observation along a period

of time in order to detect the tendencies of profitability. The analysis of the modification of the various indicators in time shows the changes of the policies and strategies of banks and/or of its business environment (Greuning and Bratanovic, 2004). A commonly used measure of bank performance is the level of bank profits (Ceylan, Emre and Asl, 2008). Bank profitability can be measured by the return on a bank's assets (ROA), a ratio of a bank's profits to its total assets. The income statements of commercial banks report profits before and after taxes. Another good measure on bank performance is the ratio of pre-tax profits to equity (ROE) rather than total assets since banks with higher equity ratio should also have a higher return on assets (Ceylan, Emre and Asl, 2008).

Bank Innovations and Profitability Simpson (2002) suggests that e-banking is driven largely by the prospects of operating costs minimization and operating revenues maximization. A comparison of online banking in developed and emerging markets revealed that in developed markets lower costs and higher revenues are more noticeable. While Sullivan (2000) finds no systematic evidence of a benefit of internet banking in US click and mortar banks. Furst, Lang and Nolle (2002) find that federally chartered US banks had higher Return on Equity (ROE) by using the click and mortar business model. Furst, Lang and Nolle (2002) also examined the determinants of internet banking adoption and observed that more profitable banks adopted internet banking after 1998 but yet they were not the first movers. Jayawardhena and Foley (2000) show that internet banking results in cost and efficiency gains for banks yet very few banks were using it and only a little more than half a million customers were online in U.K. Nader (2011) analyzed the profit efficiency of the Saudi Arabia Commercial banks during the period 1998- 2007. The results of his study indicated that availability of phone banking, number of ATMs and number of branches had a positive effect on profit efficiency of Saudi banks. On the contrary he found that the number of point of sale terminals (POSs), availability of PC banking and availability of mobile banking did not improve profit efficiency. Agboola (2006) in his study on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Banking operations in Nigeria using the nature and degree of adoption of innovative technologies; degree of utilization of the identified technologies; and the impact of the adoption of ICT devices on banks, found out that technology was the main driving force of competition in the banking industry. During his study he witnessed increase in the adoption of ATMs, EFT, smart cards, electronic home and office banking and telephone banking. He indicates that adoption of ICT improves the banks' image and leads to a wider, faster and more efficient market. He asserts that it is imperative for bank management to intensify investment in ICT products to facilitate speed, convenience, and accurate services, or otherwise lose out to their

competitors. Malhotra and Singh (2009) in their study on the impact of internet banking on bank performance and risk found out that on average internet banks are larger, more profitable and are more operationally efficient. They also found that internet banks have higher asset quality and are better managed to lower the expenses for building and equipment and that internet banks in India rely substantially on deposits. They further found out that smaller banks that adopt internet banking have been negatively impacted on profitability. Kagan, Acharya, Rao and Kodepaka (2005) in their study on whether internet banking affects the performance of community banks found that banks that provide extensive online banking services tend to perform better. They further found out that online banking helps community banks improve their earning ability as measured by return on equity and improved asset quality by reducing the proportion of overdue and underperforming assets. Hernando and Nieto (2006) while studying whether internet delivery channels change bank's performance, found out that adoption of internet as a delivery channel involved gradual reduction in overhead expenses (particularly, staff, marketing and IT) which translates to an improvement in banks' profitability. The study also indicates that internet is used as a complement to, rather than a substitute for, physical branches. The profitability gains associated with the adoption of a transactional web site are mainly explained by a significant reduction in overhead expenses. This effect is gradual, becoming significant eighteen months after adoption and reaching a maximum generally two and a half years after adoption. Their study showed that multichannel banks present statistically significant evidence of efficiency gains, that is, reduction in general expenses per unit of output. Banks would further profit from cost reductions to the extent that the Internet delivery channel functions as a substitute for traditional distribution channels. Their analysis shows that this effect varies over time and explains, in terms of cost and income structure, the main drivers of better performance. DeYoung (2005) analyzed the performance of Internet only banks versus the brick and mortar in the US market and found strong evidence of general experience effects available to all start-ups. Yet there is little evidence that technology based learning accelerates the financial performance of internet-only start-ups. He finds that bank profitability is lower for pure-play (internet-only) banks in the US market. In a later study DeYoung, Lang and Nolle (2007) analyzed the US community banks market to investigate the effect of internet banking on bank performance. They compared the brick-and-mortar banks performance to click and mortar banks which do have transactional websites over a three-year period. Their findings suggest that internet banking improved bank profitability, via increase in revenues from deposit service charges. Movements of deposits from checking accounts to money market deposit accounts,

increased use of brokered deposits, and higher average wage rates for bank employees were also observed for click and mortar banks. The internet offers a potential competitive advantage for banks and this advantage lies in the areas of cost reduction and more satisfaction of customer needs (Bradley and Stewart, 2003 and Jaruwachirathanakul and Fink, 2005). Encouraging customers to use the Internet for banking transactions can result in considerable operating costs savings (Sathye, 1999). The internet is the cheapest distribution channel for standardized bank operations, such as account management and funds transfer (Polasik and Wisniewski, 2009). Customer dissatisfaction with branch banking because of long queuing and poor customer service is an important reason for the rapid movement to electronic delivery (Karjaluoto, Mattila and Pentto, 2002). The commitment of senior management is a driving force in the adoption and exploitation of technology (Shiels, McIvor and O'Reilly, 2003).

2.10 the impact of mobile banking on financial performance.

Mobile Banking Mobile banking has increasingly been employed by many banks around the world to generate additional revenue, reduce costs or to increase customer satisfaction, often with very promising results. Unlike in the past where banks offering mobile services suffered a severe setback due to lack of customer interest and unripe technologies the time seems to be now for re-launching mobile services. Mobile banking is usually defined as carrying out banking services with the help of mobile phones or PDAs. The offered services may include transaction facilities as well as other related services that cater primarily for informational needs revolving around financial activities (Tiwari, 2006). Mobile banking started with the creation of services by banks which could be accessed through the mobile phone. These facilities aimed at enabling customers access information relating to their accounts. Subsequent innovations have seen the mobile banking phenomena continue to grow steadily. Mobile banking takes several dimensions of execution all representing a new distribution channel that allows financial institutions and other commercial actors to offer financial services outside traditional bank premises. The need for convenient ways of accessing financial resources beyond the conventional norms has seen the recurrent expansion and modernization of banking patterns. And given the huge demand for finance oriented services, institutions beside the historical banks have joined the fray in an attempt to grab a piece of the perceived cake of opportunity within the banking industry. The pent up demand for an affordable and reliable way of holding funds while ensuring that risk levels are consigned to a minimum is consistently unfolding. A system with the potential to obliterate the historical hurdles of cost and free access which have for a long time stood in the way of

willing partakers of banking services evokes immediate attention and interest. The unprecedented uptake of mobile phone banking services in Kenya is a testament to this fact (Wambari, 2009). Porteous (2006) distinguishes two aspects of mobile banking: Additive and transformational characteristics. Additive aspects are those in which the mobile phone is merely another channel to an existing bank account. Mobile banking is additive when it merely adds to the range of choices or enhances the convenience of existing customers of mainstream financial institutions. Transformational characteristics arise when the financial product linked to the use of the phone is targeted at persons who do not hold formal bank accounts with the conventional banking institutions. It is therefore imperative to understand the business environment in which banks operate and identify customer groups that the banks may seek to target via Mobile banking. For instance many people do not own bank accounts but own mobile phones and this unbanked population possesses/ controls huge chunk of money running into billions of shillings which is not banked as witnessed in M-pesa transactions which runs into billions since its advent (Asongu, 2012). As a result this clientele have been brought on board to main banking stream thereby enabling banks tap on the resources much needed to grow their revenue base as well as their customer base as occasioned in the recent launch of M-shwari partnership between Commercial Bank of Africa with Safaricom which is going to reach many unbanked population. Mobile banking enhances the number of existing channels of distribution that a bank employs to offer its services. The effect of a distribution channel can be measured by its fulfilment of three objectives which are closely related to each other. These are increasing sales volume, reducing costs of distribution and increasing customer satisfaction. One of the primary tasks of a distribution channel is to increase the volume of demand for products at profitable prices. This object is arrived by increasing operations efficiency so that those losses /costs are minimized that are caused by delays in catering to customer orders. Further a favourable reputation of the firm's logistical capacity may help generate additional orders. Mobile banking contributes to achieving this goal by following means: anytime anywhere access to banking services; availability of push services to suggest transaction on an urgent basis. According to Jonathan & Camilo (2009), most mobile transactions in the developing world enable users to do three things: Store value (currency) in an account accessible via a handset. When the user already has a bank account, this is generally a question of linking to a bank account. If the user does not have an account, then the process creates a bank account for him/her or creates a pseudo bank account, held by a third party or the user's mobile operator; Convert cash into and out of the store value account. When the account is linked to a bank account, then users can visit banks to

cash-in and cash-out. In many instances, users can also visit the GSM providers' retail stores. According to Demombynes&Thegeya (2012), on the one hand a partially integrated product clearly delineates the role of the bank (which provides and owns banking services) from that of the mobile service provider (which provides mobile telephony infrastructure and controls the agent network). Thus the bank compensates the mobile service provider for access to the network and enjoys the remaining profits. This type of contract more closely looks like a debt contract between parties. On the other hand, a fully integrated solution may not draw the same distinction between bank and mobile service providers. In this case, the distribution of surplus is contingent on the relative bargaining power of the bank and mobile service provider. This sort of contract more closely resembles an equity contract between two parties. Equity-like contracts are more likely to be complex and therefore more difficult to negotiate than debt-like contracts, there-by presenting a potential hurdle towards the goal of increasing access. The internet and the Mobile phone-two technological advancements that have profoundly affected human behaviour in the last decade- have started to converge. The products of this association are mobile data services. Using a variety of platforms, services are being created to enable mobile devices to perform many activities of the traditional internet albeit in a reduced format for mobile devices. One area of activity is mobile banking –one of the first areas of commercial transaction on the wireless internet. Banking is an area that has extended in many different ways in recent years, including telephone and online banking. Mobile banking provides yet another channel for banking services in emerging market, provides some possibility for becoming a primary channel. The spread of mobile phones across the developing world is one of the most remarkable technology strides of the past decade. Buoyed by prepaid cards and inexpensive handsets, hundreds of millions of first time telephone owners have made voice calls and text messages part of their daily lives. However many of these new mobile phone users live in informal and or cash economies, without access to financial services that others take for granted. Indeed across the developing world there are probably more people with mobile handsets than with bank accounts (Porteous, 2006). Various initiatives use mobile phones to provide financial services to the unbanked. These services take a variety of forms including long distance remittances, micropayments and informal airtime bartering schemes –all go by various names including mobile banking, mobile transfers and mobile payments. The terms M-banking, M-payments, M-transfer and M-finance refer collectively to a set of applications that enable people to use their mobile telephones to manipulate their bank accounts, store value in an account linked to their handsets, transfer funds or even access credit or insurance products. The first target for

these applications was consumers in the developed world. By complementing services offered by the banking system, such as cheque books, ATMs, Voice mail/landline interfaces, smart cards, point of sale networks and internet resources, the mobile platform offers a convenient additional method for managing money without handling cash (Karjaluo, 2002). For users in the developing world the appeal of these Mobile banking / M-payments systems may be less about convenience and more about accessibility and affordability.

2.12 The impact of internet banking on financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya||customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is one of the keystone concepts in strategic marketing. Its determinants and consequents have been rather well studied over the last 30 years. Not only do academicians admit the importance of customer satisfaction for a firm's development but also practitioners and businessmen pay great attention to its measurement and management. The intuition behind the view that customer satisfaction is important is straightforward. Satisfied customers tend to demonstrate loyal behaviour (Fornell, 1992; Anderson & Sullivan, 1993; Wangenheim & Bayon, 2004). They prefer the firm to its competitors; they are less price sensitive and they attract new customers through word-of-mouth. Ultimately customer satisfaction through loyalty leads to higher revenues and to better financial performance. As can be implied from this intuitive framework, customer satisfaction does not have an immediate impact on a firm's financial performance. There is a theoretical foundation (ECSI Technical Committee, 1998; EPSI, 2011; Gonzalez Menorca, Fernandez-Ortiza, Fuentes Lombardo, & Clavel San Emeterio, 2016) for the claim that increased customer satisfaction in a particular period will be transmitted to loyalty and further affect revenue some one or two periods later. This reasoning is based on the assumption that an increase in customer satisfaction is not only associated with better firm performance but also allows for its prediction. Thus, the research question arises: to what extent can lagged customer satisfaction predict banks' financial performance. To this is added the question of how loyalty is involved in this process and how it affects financial outcomes. If it were the case that loyalty was a channel that transmits customer satisfaction to financial performance, then it could not predict financial results and instead, it must be associated with results in the current period. Thus, we are interested in testing the predictive ability of loyalty as well. Two factors have motivated this study. First, using customer satisfaction as a predictor for a firm's performance is a valuable tool both for firm management and investors. For the former customer satisfaction can serve as a diagnostic tool,

for the latter as an indicator for prospective growth. It is extremely important for conservative, well-established industries since competition is usually fierce in such industries. The market is already divided between main companies thus regular growth indicators are not fully applicable for the prediction of performance. Banking and insurance in high-income countries are examples of such well-developed industries for which customer satisfaction can be a useful indicator of future financial performance. Second, an empirical test of loyalty as a predictor of financial performance, or the absence of such a relation, can be useful for making management decisions. Top-managers usually tend to set up the key performance indicators (KPIs) for employees based on loyalty or loyalty-related indices such as, for example, the Net Promoter Score (NPS) (Reichheld, 2003; Reichheld, 2006). However, if loyalty is the consequence of customer satisfaction, then it only reflects the efforts that were undertaken in previous periods. Then it cannot be really managed and what can be managed is the customer satisfaction. Thus, testing loyalty as a financial performance predictor can challenge the practice of using it as KPI for employees. In this study, we have a unique opportunity to make use of panel data with eleven years of observations for the eight main international Scandinavian banks. Our first contribution is to test the predictive ability of customer satisfaction in relation to financial performance. Secondly, we test the predictive ability of loyalty in relation to financial results and by doing so we are indirectly testing the mechanism through which customer satisfaction is transmitted into financial results. This paper represents an integral part of a series of studies joined under the project 'Linkage between customer satisfaction and financial performance'. The Project approach is further introduced and discussed by Adolphson, Eklof, and Parmler (2012). The current paper continues the discussion of the influence of customer satisfaction on financial performance in banking (Eklof, Hellstrom, Parmler, Malova, & Podkorytova, 2016) (Golovkova, Eklof, Podkorytova, & Malova, forthcoming). The outline of the paper is as follows. After the introduction, in section 2 we survey and briefly describe previous research in the field of interest and finalise by specifying our formal research questions. Section 3 is devoted to the data and research design. In section 4 we present and comment on the main empirical results of the research, and section 5 discusses caveats of the research and gives some conclusions, as well as proposals for further research.

2.14 The comparison between Banking and financial performance:

The banking sector is considered to be an important source of financing for most businesses. The common assumption, which underpins much of the financial performance research and discussion, is that increasing financial performance will lead to improved functions and activities of the

organizations. The subject of financial performance and research into its measurement is well advanced within finance and management fields. It can be argued that there are three principal factors to improve financial performance for financial institutions; the institution size, its asset management, and the operational efficiency. To date, there has been little published studies to explore the impact of these factors on the financial performance, especially the commercial banks. This study proposes that there are measurable linkages among bank's size, asset management, the operational efficiency, and the financial performance. The purpose of this study is to analyze the financial data of Omani commercial banks for the financial periods 1999-2003. in addition, to examine the relationships among measures such as bank's size, operational efficiency, asset management, return on assets (ROA), interest income, and to discuss their impact on the bank's performance. Financial analysis is used to quantitatively examine the differences in performance among commercial banks in Oman, and the banks are ranked based on their financial measures and performance for each bank. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to classify the commercial banks in Oman on the basis of their financial characteristics as a guide line for future development, and to assess their financial performance. In order to evaluate the internal performance of a commercial bank, financial indicators are constructed from the bank financial statements. Financial ratios like ROA, asset utilization, and operational efficiency are calculated, Also, measures as assets size, and the interest income size are used to assess the performance of a commercial bank. However, it is hypothesized for this study that there exist positive correlations among return on assets, asset management, operational efficiency, bank size, and the interest income size. In addition, there exist an impact of asset management, operational efficiency, and the bank's size on the financial performance of the bank. Thus, this study is organized as follows: the next section following the introduction discusses the relevant literature. The third section defines the banking sector in Oman. Methodology of the study is described in fourth section. The fifth section provides details of the results and analysis of the available data, and the final section presents the main conclusions.

2.15 The impact of banking regulations on banks' cost and profit efficiency

As banks operate in one of the most heavily regulated environments, research in banking regulations and their effect on bank performance and stability has long attracted both theoretical and empirical

interest. At the international level, Barth et al. (2004) investigate the effect of a broad range of regulatory and supervisory measures on bank stability, development and performance, while Demirguc-Kunt et al. (2008) and Pasiouras et al. (2006) study the effect of similar measures on banks' overall soundness, as measured by credit ratings. Similarly, other studies have examined the effect of regulations on banking sector crises (Demirguc-Kunt and Detragiache, 2002, Beck et al., 2006a) and banks' risk-taking behaviour (Gonzalez, 2005; Laeven and Levine, 2009). An issue that has received comparatively little attention, however, is what impact the regulatory environment has on bank efficiency, as opposed to other measures of bank performance. This paper seeks to address this issue by offering international evidence on the cost and profit efficiency of banks.

Prior studies in the literature have sought to account for the influence of banking regulations as part of the environmental factors affecting bank efficiency. Dietsch and Lozano-Vivas (2000), for example, highlight the impact of differences in the environmental conditions on banks' cost efficiency, using a sample of Spanish and French banks. Similarly, multi-country studies that examine sources of differences in bank efficiency account for country-specific differences in the economic, financial or technological environments using aggregate measures such as market capitalization, GDP growth, number of banks or ATMs per population, etc. In accounting for regulatory influences, however, these studies have, owing to data limitations, resorted to use of simple proxies such as the degree of market concentration, industry average capital, industry average profitability, and intermediation ratios (e.g. Dietsch and Lozano-Vivas, 2000). Similarly, Grigorian and Manole (2002), in examining bank efficiency differences for the transition countries of Eastern Europe and former Soviet Union, account for the influence of regulatory measures such as capital adequacy ratio, maximum exposure to single borrower and limits on foreign exchange open positions. Furthermore, a few recent studies, also focussing on transition countries, have used the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) index of banking sector reform among the environmental factors affecting bank efficiency (e.g. Fries and Taci, 2005).¹

Most recently, Pasiouras (2008) tackles the issue at the cross-country level by employing a broad range of regulatory and supervision measures developed by the World Bank (Barth et al., 2001b) to investigate the technical efficiency of banks. Using data envelopment analysis (DEA) and Tobit regressions on a sample of 715 banks operating in 95 countries during 2003, he finds that banks' technical efficiency is positively influenced in some regressions by capital adequacy standards,

powerful supervisory agencies and market discipline mechanisms (the latter being significant in all his regressions).

The present paper provides further international evidence in relation to the impact of the regulatory environment by focussing on the cost and profit efficiency of banks. The specific regulations of concern in this paper are related to restrictions on banks' activities and the three pillars of Basel II, namely capital requirements (Pillar 1), official supervisory power (Pillar 2), and market discipline mechanisms (Pillar 3). While around 100 countries have stated their intention to adopt Basel II, there is an on-going debate about the costs and benefits of the proposed regulatory approaches (Barth et al., 2006). Hence, the importance of our study lies in providing cross-country analysis and evidence relating to some of the enduring questions about the impact of the new regulatory framework for the banking industry.

While the present study is related to Pasiouras (2008) in studying the impact of regulations on bank efficiency, it is fundamentally different in three respects. The first and probably the most important is that we examine the impact on cost and profit efficiency of banks. Cost efficiency is a wider concept than technical efficiency, since it refers to both technical and allocative efficiency. Profit efficiency is an even wider concept as it combines both costs and revenues in the measurement of efficiency.² Maudos et al. (2002) point out that the estimation of profit efficiency and its comparison to cost efficiency, and international efficiency comparisons are two areas where the available evidence on bank efficiency is very limited. Thus, our study contributes in bridging this gap, while at the same time provides statistical evidence of the association of these two efficiency measures with capital requirements, official supervisory power, market discipline, and restriction on bank activities. Second, we use stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) rather than DEA. The main advantage of SFA over DEA is that it allows us to distinguish between inefficiency and other stochastic shocks in the estimation of efficiency scores (Yildirim and Philippatos, 2007). Finally, our sample is more representative as we use panel data over the period 2000–2004 rather than cross-section data at one point in time (i.e. 2003); it has been argued that efficiency is better studied and modelled with panels (Coelli et al., 2005).³

As noted in the Introduction section, our paper is also related in spirit to recent studies that provide international evidence on the impact of regulations and supervision on banks' performance (e.g. Barth et al., 2002, Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2004). In contrast to these studies, which mainly use financial ratios

as indicators of performance, we measure bank efficiency using an efficient frontier technique. Berger and Humphrey (1997) emphasise that efficient frontier approaches are superior when compared to traditional measures of performance (e.g. return on assets, cost/revenue), since they account simultaneously for relevant inputs and outputs of a bank, as well as for differences in the input prices. Furthermore, they offer an overall objective numerical score and ranking that complies with an optimization mechanism.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a brief background discussion on the impact of regulations on bank performance. Section 3 covers the methodological issues and data for our empirical work. Section 4 discusses the empirical results, and Section 5 concludes.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter defines and describes the research methodology to reach the research objectives and goals. Research methodology is a collective term for the structured

process of conducting research. Research methodologies are used in academic research to test hypotheses. The research methodology consists of research design,

sampling technique, data collection, and data analysis.

3.1 Research design

A research design is a strategy for gathering and analyzing data in order to obtain desired information with sufficient precision or to properly test a hypothesis. This The study's design will be descriptive,

which means it will describe the problem at hand. In this type of design, the researcher only describes the problem based on the data provided by the sample, without any analysis.

Descriptive research is usually defined as a type of quantitative research, though

Qualitative research can also be used for descriptive purposes. The research design should be carefully developed to ensure that the results are valid and reliable.

When the goal of the research is to identify characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories, descriptive research is an excellent choice. It is useful when not much is known. yet about the topic or problem. Before you can research why something happens, you need to understand how, when, and where it happens.

3.2 Target accessible population

The target population of this study is the residents of Mogadishu, the capital of Somalia. However, this population is so large and scattered that the sample cannot be drawn from the whole of it, other researchers will use the accessible population. The target This study's accessible population will be 80 respondents from some selected banks in Mogadishu, Somalia, especially Salam Somali Bank, Premier Bank, and IBS.

Table 3.2.1: Study Population:

No	Banks	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Salam Somali Bank	40	50%
2.	Dahabshiil Bank	25	31%
3.	Premier Bank	15	19%
4.	Total	80	100%

3.3 Sample size

The sample for this study will be 50 out of 80 people from Salam Somali Bank, Premier Bank, and IBS in Mogadishu, Somalia. This figure has shifted in response to population growth. Slovenia's formula governs sample size:

$n = \frac{N}{(N+1) * e^2}$ where n: is the sample size, N: is the population, and (e)² is the standard error of the mean.

$n = 100 / (101 * (0.141)^2)$; thus, the sample size is 50 respondents.

n= required sample size

N= target population

e= error

Table 3.3.1: Sample size

No	Banks	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Salam Somali Bank	25	50%
2.	Dahabshiil Bank	15	30%
3.	Premier Bank	10	20%
4.	Total	50	100%

3.4. Sampling method or technique:

During sampling, the researcher will use a stratified sampling method that is stratified by Sampling involves dividing the population into subpopulations that may differ in important ways. It allows you to draw more precise conclusions by ensuring that every subgroup is properly represented in the sample. To stratify means to divide or classify people into groups based on certain characteristics such as position, rank, or status, income, education, sex, or ethnic background. These separate groupings are referred to as subset so subgroups. Stratified sampling will be used in this study because stratified Random samples are generally more accurate in representing the population than are simple random samples.

3.5 Data Collection Instrument

As far as data collection tools were concerned, the conduction of the research involved the use of semi-structured questionnaire, which was used as an interview guide for the researcher. Some certain questions were prepared, so as for the researcher to guide the interview towards the satisfaction of research objectives, but additional questions were made encountered during the interviews.

3.6 Data Collecting Procedure

A questionnaire will be conducted in this study as the primary tool for collecting data. Because of the nature of the research and the timing, the questionnaire is appropriate for this study. This method has unintended consequences. The researcher also uses closed-ended questions to get data from a limited number of respondents; the data will be collected by the researcher and his assistants, although he could not reach such an area.

3.7 Data analysis

This section covers the analysis of data collected from target respondents. The analysis was done by using SPSS and Microsoft Excel. Tables are used to present the findings of the analysis. and figures, 80 of the respondents for the study were each issued one questionnaire. 50 out of the 80 questionnaires issued were returned. Data analysis can be divided into 1) quantitative data analysis and 2) qualitative data analysis. Qualitative data Analysis will be used for this research, which is the process of transforming raw data into usable information, often presented in the form of published articles, in order to value to the statistical output. or the process of evaluating data using analytical reasoning to examine each component of the data provided. Quantitative data analysis is best because it focuses on numbers or quantities and bases the results on them. numerical analysis. Computer software was used to tabulate and cross-tabulate the data.

3.8 Research quality:

Reliability and validity are closely related, but they mean different things. A Measurement can be reliable without being valid. However, if a measurement is invalid, it is usually reliable.

3.8.1 Validity of the instrument

The validity of the instrument is related to the instruments' relevance to study objectives; in other words, the instruments' ability to measure what they are supposed to measure and the data collected accurately represents the respondent's opinions.

3.8.2 Reliability of the instrument

Validity refers to how accurately a method measures what it is intended to measure. If the validity of the research is high, which means that the results correspond to reality,

properties, characteristics, and variations in the physical or social world High reliability is one indicator that a measurement is invalid. If a method is not reliable, it probably isn't valid. (Middleton,2021)

To ensure reliability, a pretest will be performed prior to data collection from the questionnaire. Five questionnaires will be distributed to five people from the target population.

population and will be requested to answer them. After a few days, five identical questionnaires will be distributed to the same respondents, and they will be scored.

Two dates can be compared. If the two datasets are similar, then the questionnaire is reliable.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

The current study was subject to certain ethical issues. As it was mentioned earlier, all participants reported their written acceptance regarding their participation in the research, through a signed Consent and Briefing Letter. At the same time, sample members were asked to sign a Debriefing and Withdrawal Letter. The aim of both letters was to reassure participants that their participation in the research is voluntary and that they were free to withdraw from it at any point and for any reason.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presented the analysis of the data and its interpretation. Descriptive analysis was done using frequency tables, charts, mean and standard deviation.

1. What is your gender?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	22	44.0	44.0	44.0
Valid Female	28	56.0	56.0	100.0

Total	50	100.0	100.0
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Figure 4.1 Gender of the respondents:

The Most of respondents of this study 44 (90%) were male and only 28(56%) Were female the researcher indicates the most of respondents were male. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were male, while small number of the respondents were female.

2. What is your age?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-24	11	22.0	22.0	22.0
25-34	24	48.0	48.0	70.0
35-44	15	30.0	30.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Age of the respondents:

The Most of respondents of this study 11 (22%) were 18-24 and 24(48%) Were 25-34 and 15(30%) Were 35-44, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were 25-34. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were 25-34, while small number of the respondents were 18-24.

3. What is the highest degree you have completed?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Bachelor's degree	28	56.0	56.0	56.0
Master's degree	22	44.0	44.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 the highest degree of the respondents:

The Most of respondents of this study 28 (56%) were Bachelor's degree and 22 (44%) Were Master's degree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Bachelor's degree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Bachelor's degree, while small number of the respondents were Master's degree.

4. How frequently do you use internet banking services?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	11	22.0	22.0	22.0
Weekly	24	48.0	48.0	70.0
Valid Monthly	2	4.0	4.0	74.0
Rarely	13	26.0	26.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 using internet banking services of the respondents:

The Most of respondents of this study 11 (22%) were Daily and 24 (48%) Were Weekly and 2 (4%) Were Monthly and 13 (26%) Were rarely, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Weekly. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Weekly, while small number of the respondents were Monthly.

5. In your opinion, how has internet banking affected your financial performance?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Improved it significantly	32	64.0	64.0	64.0
Valid Worsened it somewhat	1	2.0	2.0	66.0
No impact	17	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 How has internet banking affected your financial performance:

The Most of respondents of this study 32 (64%) were Improved it significantly and 1 (2%) Were Worsened it somewhat and 17 (34%) Were No impact, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Improved it significantly. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Improved it significantly, while small number of the respondents were Worsened it somewhat.

6. Have you noticed any changes in your spending habits since using internet banking?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes, I spend less	6	12.0	12.0	12.0

No, my spending habits remain the same	20	40.0	40.0	52.0
Yes, I spend more	24	48.0	48.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Have you noticed any changes in your spending habits since using internet banking:

The Most of respondents of this study 6 (12%) were Yes, I spend less and 20 (40%) Were No, my spending habits remain the same and 24 (48%) Were Yes, I spend more, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Yes, I spend more. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Yes, I spend more, while small number of the respondents were Yes, I spend less.

7. Do you think internet banking has made managing your finances easier?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes, significantly easier	29	58.0	58.0	58.0
No, it has made no difference	21	42.0	42.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Do you think internet banking has made managing your finances easier:

The Most of respondents of this study 29(58%) were Yes, significantly easier, and 21(42%) Were No, it has made no difference; the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Yes, significantly easier. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Yes, significantly easier, while small number of the respondents were No, it has made no difference.

8. Overall, how satisfied are you with your internet banking experience?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	11	22.0	22.0	22.0
Somewhat dissatisfied	1	2.0	2.0	24.0
Somewhat satisfied	14	28.0	28.0	52.0
Very dissatisfied	1	2.0	2.0	54.0
Very satisfied	23	46.0	46.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 how satisfied are you with your internet banking experience:

The Most of respondents of this study 11 (22%) were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, and 1 (2%) Were somewhat dissatisfied and 14 (28%) Were somewhat satisfied and 1 (2%) Were Very dissatisfied and 23 (46%) Were Very satisfied, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Very satisfied. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Very satisfied, while small number of the respondents were somewhat dissatisfied and Very dissatisfied.

9. The use of mobile banking enhances the flow of money, which improves the country's finances.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	4	8.0	8.0	8.0
Disagree	1	2.0	2.0	10.0
Neutral	13	26.0	26.0	36.0
Strongly Agree	26	52.0	52.0	88.0
Strongly disagree	6	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 the use of mobile banking enhances the flow of money, which improves the country's finances:

The Most of respondents of this study 4 (8%) were agree, and 1 (2%) Were disagree and 13 (26%) Were Neutral and 26 (52%) Were Strongly Agree and 6 (12%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Strongly Agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Strongly Agree, while small number of the respondents were somewhat dissatisfied and Disagree.

10. Mobile Banking reduces the workload of employees

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	17	34.0	34.0	34.0
Disagree	3	6.0	6.0	40.0
Neutral	20	40.0	40.0	80.0
strongly agree	8	16.0	16.0	96.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0	4.0	100.0

Total	50	100.0	100.0
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Figure 4.1 Mobile Banking reduces the workload of employees:

The Most of respondents of this study 17 (34%) were agree, and 3 (6%) Were disagree and 20 (40%) Were Neutral and 8 (16%) Were Strongly Agree and 2 (4%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Neutral. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Neutral, while small number of the respondents were Strongly disagree.

11. Mobile banking increases the satisfaction of the clients.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	15	30.0	30.0	30.0
Disagree	9	18.0	18.0	48.0
Neutral	11	22.0	22.0	70.0
Strongly agree	10	20.0	20.0	90.0
Strongly disagree	5	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Mobile banking increases the satisfaction of the clients:

The Most of respondents of this study 15 (30%) were agree, and 9 (18%) Were disagree and 11 (22%) Were Neutral and 10 (20%) Were Strongly Agree and 5 (10%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were agree, while small number of the respondents were Strongly disagree.

12. Mobile banking increases money circulation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	15	30.0	30.0	30.0
Disagree	9	18.0	18.0	48.0
Neutral	11	22.0	22.0	70.0
Strongly agree	10	20.0	20.0	90.0
Strongly disagree	5	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Mobile banking increases the satisfaction of the clients:

The Most of respondents of this study 15 (30%) were agree, and 9 (18%) Were disagree and 11 (22%) Were Neutral and 10 (20%) Were Strongly Agree and 5 (10%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were agree, while small number of the respondents were Strongly disagree.

13. How often do you use banking services in Mogadishu?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	38	76.0	76.0	76.0
Weekly	4	8.0	8.0	84.0
Valid Monthly	6	12.0	12.0	96.0
Rarely	2	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 How often do you use banking services in Mogadishu:

The Most of respondents of this study 38 (76%) were Daily and 4 (8%) Were Weekly and 6 (12%) Were Monthly and 2 (4%) Were rarely, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were daily. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were daily, while small number of the respondents were rarely.

14. Have you noticed any changes in the cost of banking services in Mogadishu over the past year?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes, they have become more expensive	25	50.0	50.0	50.0
Valid No, they have remained the same	25	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 How often do you use banking services in Mogadishu:

The Most of respondents of this study 25 (50%) were Yes, they have become more expensive and 25 (50%) Were No, they have remained the same, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Yes, they have become more expensive. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Yes, they have become more expensive, while small number of the respondents were No, they have remained the same.

15. Have you noticed any changes in the quality of banking services in Mogadishu over the past year?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes, they have improved	45	90.0	90.0	90.0
Valid No, they have declined	5	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Have you noticed any changes in the quality of banking services in Mogadishu over the past year:

The Most of respondents of this study 45 (90%) were Yes, they have improved and 5 (10%) Were No, they have declined; the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Yes, they have improved. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Yes, they have improved, while small number of the respondents were No, they have declined.

16. Have you noticed any changes in the time it takes to perform banking transactions in Mogadishu over the past year?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes, it has become faster	29	58.0	58.0	58.0
Valid No, it has remained the same	21	42.0	42.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Have you noticed any changes in the time it takes to perform banking transactions in Mogadishu over the past year:

The Most of respondents of this study 29 (58%) were Yes, it has become faster and 21 (42%) Were No, it has remained the same; the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Yes, it has become faster. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Yes, it has become faster, while small number of the respondents were No, it has remained the same.

17. Have you used any new banking services or products in Mogadishu over the past year?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Maybe	3	6.0	6.0	6.0
Valid Yes	19	38.0	38.0	44.0
No	28	56.0	56.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Have you used any new banking services or products in Mogadishu over the past year:

The Most of respondents of this study 3 (6%) were Maybe and 19 (38%) Were Yes, and 28 (56%) Were No, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were No, it has become faster. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were No, it has become faster, while small number of the respondents were maybe.

18. If yes, which new banking services or products have you used in Mogadishu over the past year?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
idman community bank	1	2.0	2.0	2.0
Primary Bank.	15	30.0	30.0	32.0
Valid Salam Somali Bank	27	54.0	54.0	86.0
Som bank	7	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

19. Have these new banking services or products had any impact on your income in Mogadishu?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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	Yes, they have increased my income	16	32.0	32.0	32.0
Valid	No, they have had no impact on my income	34	68.0	68.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Have you noticed any changes in the time it takes to perform banking transactions in Mogadishu over the past year:

The Most of respondents of this study 16 (32%) were Yes, they have increased my income and 34 (68%) Were No, they have had no impact on my income; the researcher indicates the most of respondents were No, they have had no impact on my income. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were No, they have had no impact on my income, while small number of the respondents were Yes, they have increased my income.

21. Cost: Banking innovation can reduce the cost of banking services by automating processes and reducing the need for physical infrastructure. This can lead to lower fees and charges for customers in Mogadishu.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Agree	6	12.0	12.0
	Neutral	1	2.0	14.0
	Disagree	11	22.0	36.0
Valid	Strongly agree	29	58.0	94.0
	Strongly disagree	3	6.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0

Figure 4.1 Banking innovation can reduce the cost of banking services by automating processes and reducing the need for physical infrastructure. This can lead to lower fees and charges for customers in Mogadishu:

The Most of respondents of this study 6 (12%) were agree, and 1 (2%) Were Neutral and 11 (22%) Were disagree and 29 (58%) Were Strongly Agree and 3 (6%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Strongly Agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Strongly Agree, while small number of the respondents were Neutral.

22. Quality: Banking innovation can improve the quality of banking services by providing more convenient and accessible services, such as mobile banking and online banking. This can result in a better customer experience and increased customer satisfacti

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	24	48.0	48.0	48.0
Neutral	1	2.0	2.0	50.0
Disagree	13	26.0	26.0	76.0
Strongly agree	8	16.0	16.0	92.0
Strongly disagree	4	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Quality: Banking innovation can improve the quality of banking services by providing more convenient and accessible services, such as mobile banking and online banking. This can result in a better customer experience and increased customer satisfaction:

The Most of respondents of this study 24 (48%) were agree, and 1 (2%) Were Neutral and 13 (26%) Were disagree and 8 (16%) Were Strongly Agree and 4 (8%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Agree, while small number of the respondents were Neutral.

23. Time: Banking innovation can save time for customers by enabling them to perform transactions quickly and easily, without having to visit a physical bank branch. This can also save time for banks by automating processes and reducing manual work.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	15	30.0	30.0	30.0
Neutral	1	2.0	2.0	32.0
Disagree	11	22.0	22.0	54.0
Strongly agree	22	44.0	44.0	98.0
Strongly disagree	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Quality: Banking innovation can improve the quality of banking services by providing more convenient and accessible services, such as mobile banking and online banking. This can result in a better customer experience and increased customer satisfaction:

The Most of respondents of this study 15 (30%) were agree, and 1 (2%) Were Neutral and 11 (24%) Were disagree and 22 (44%) Were Strongly Agree and 1 (2%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Strongly agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Strongly agree, while small number of the respondents were Strongly disagree.

24. Flexibility: Banking innovation can provide more flexibility for customers by offering a wider range of services and products, such as digital wallets and peer-to-peer payments. This can enable customers to manage their finances more effectively and

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	7	14.0	14.0	14.0
Neutral	2	4.0	4.0	18.0
Valid Disagree	19	38.0	38.0	56.0
Strongly agree	22	44.0	44.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 Flexibility: Banking innovation can provide more flexibility for customers by offering a wider range of services and products, such as digital wallets and peer-to-peer payments. This can enable customers to manage their finances more effectively and:

The Most of respondents of this study 7 (14%) were agree, and 2 (4%) Were Neutral and 19 (38%) Were disagree and 22 (44%) Were Strongly Agree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Strongly agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Strongly agree, while small number of the respondents were natural.

25. the internet banking reduces the need for customers to visit physical banks,

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	26	52.0	52.0	52.0
Valid Neutral	2	4.0	4.0	56.0
Disagree	1	2.0	2.0	58.0

Strongly agree	19	38.0	38.0	96.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 the internet banking reduces the need for customers to visit physical banks:

The Most of respondents of this study 26 (52%) were agree, and 2 (4%) Were Neutral and 1 (2%) Were disagree and 19 (38%) Were Strongly Agree and 2 (4%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were agree, while small number of the respondents were disagree.

26. The online Banking provides more convenient and timely access to financial products, and increases the efficiency of financial transactions.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	18	36.0	36.0	36.0
Strongly agree	15	30.0	30.0	66.0
Valid Strongly disagree	16	32.0	32.0	98.0
5.00	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1 The online Banking provides more convenient and timely access to financial products, and increases the efficiency of financial transactions:

The Most of respondents of this study 18 (36%) were agree, and 15 (30%) Were Strongly Agree and 16 (32%) Were Strongly disagree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were agree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were agree, while small number of the respondents were Strongly Agree.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

This chapter provides the summary of the findings, the conclusions from the study, recommendations for policy and practice, the study limitations and finally suggestions for further research:

Discussion of the Major Findings

The Most of respondents of this study 44 (90%) were male and only 28(56%) Were female the researcher indicates the most of respondents were male. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were male, while small number of the respondents were female. The Most of respondents of this study 11 (22%) were 18-24 and 24(48%) Were 25-34 and 15(30%) Were 35-44, the researcher

indicates the most of respondents were 25-34. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were 25-34, while small number of the respondents were 18-24.

The Most of respondents of this study 28 (56%) were Bachelor's degree and 22 (44%) Were Master's degree, the researcher indicates the most of respondents were Bachelor's degree. Based on data gathered; the majority of respondents were Bachelor's degree, while small number of the respondents were Master's degree.

The respondents were asked that “How frequently do they use internet banking services?”

The Most of respondents of this study 6 (12%) were Yes, I spend less and 24 (48%) Were Yes, I spend more.

The respondents were asked that “In your opinion, how has internet banking affected your financial performance?”

The Most of respondents of this study 32 (64%) were Improved it significantly and 17 (34%) Were No impact.

The respondents were asked that “Have you noticed any changes in your spending habits since using internet banking?”

The Most of respondents of this study 6 (12%) were Yes, I spend less and 24 (48%) Were Yes, I spend more, The findings of this questionnaire indicate that a significant portion of respondents have noticed changes in their spending habits since using internet banking. While a small percentage reported spending less, the majority reported spending more. This suggests that internet banking may have a potential impact on consumer behavior and financial decision-making. Further research may be necessary to explore the reasons behind these changes in spending habits and to develop strategies to promote responsible financial management among internet banking users.

The respondents were asked that “how satisfied are you with your internet banking experience?”

The Most of respondents of this study 11 (22%) were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, and 23 (46%) Were Very satisfied, The findings of this questionnaire show that a significant portion of respondents

are satisfied with their internet banking experience. Almost half of the respondents reported being very satisfied, while a smaller proportion reported being dissatisfied. These results suggest that internet banking may be a convenient and effective way for individuals to manage their finances. However, the internet banking where satisfied with because of accessibility, ease of use, and the ability to manage finances from anywhere at any time. Internet banking also offers various services such as bill payments, fund transfers, and account management, which make it a preferred choice for many customers. Additionally, internet banking is generally secure and provides multiple layers of authentication to protect customer information and transactions.

The respondents were asked that “ The use of mobile banking enhances the flow of money, which improves the country's finances.

The Most of respondents of this study 4 (8%) were agree, and 6 (12%) Were Strongly disagree. According to the findings of the questionnaire, a majority of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the use of mobile banking enhances the flow of money and improves the country's finances. Specifically, 8% of the respondents agreed with the statement, while 12% strongly disagreed. The remaining respondents may have had a neutral or mixed opinion on the matter. Further analysis would be required to understand the reasons behind these responses and their implications for the adoption and promotion of mobile banking in the country.

The respondents were also asked “**Mobile Banking reduces the workload of employees**”

The Most of respondents of this study 17 (34%) were agree, and 2 (4%) Were Strongly disagree, Mobile banking reduces the workload of employees because it allows customers to perform banking transactions on their own, without the need for assistance from bank employees. This means that employees can focus on other tasks, such as customer service, rather than spending time on routine transactions. Mobile banking also reduces the need for physical paperwork and reduces the time required for processing transactions, which further reduces the workload of employees. Overall, mobile banking streamlines the banking process and makes it more efficient, which benefits both customers and employees.

The respondents were also asked “**Mobile banking increases money circulation**”

The Most of respondents of this study 15 (30%) were agree, and 5 (10%) Were strongly disagree, Mobile banking contributes to an increase in the circulation of money. Mobile banking enables customers to conduct financial transactions at any time and from any location, simply by using their mobile device. This high level of accessibility has led to an increase in the number of people who are engaging in financial transactions. Additionally, it has significantly reduced the need for physical cash, as customers can easily transfer money from their bank accounts to any other bank account using their mobile devices.

Another way that mobile banking has increased money circulation is by providing access to financial services to people who were previously unbanked. In many developing countries, access to basic financial services such as bank accounts, loans and savings accounts was a challenge. With mobile banking, however, anyone with a mobile device can access these services. This has led to an increase in the number of people who are engaging in financial transactions, which in turn has led to an increase in money circulation in the economy.

Mobile banking has also made it easier for people to save money, which has further increased money circulation. Mobile banking apps now allow people to save money by setting up direct debits, and even by rounding up their purchases and depositing the difference into their savings account. This has led to an increase in the amount of money that is being saved, which in turn has increased the amount of money that is being circulated in the economy.

In conclusion, mobile banking has had a significant impact on money circulation in the economy. By providing access to financial services to a wider range of people, increasing accessibility, and making it easier to save money, mobile banking has contributed to an increase in the amount of money that is being circulated in the economy.

They also questioned that the **Banking innovation can reduce the cost of banking services by automating processes and reducing the need for physical infrastructure. This can lead to lower fees and charges for customers in Mogadishu.**

The Most of respondents of this study 6 (12%) were agree and 3 (6%) Were Strongly disagree,

This, in turn, can lead to lower fees and charges for customers.

One way that banking innovation can reduce the cost of banking services is through the implementation of digital banking. Digital banking can automate many banking processes that traditionally required physical infrastructure and personnel, such as tellers and branches. This can significantly reduce the cost of banking services as banks no longer need to pay for expensive infrastructure and staff. With digital banking, customers can conduct financial transactions remotely, such as opening a bank account, transferring funds, and even applying for loans. This can significantly reduce operational costs, which in turn can reduce fees and charges for customers.

Another way that banking innovation can reduce the cost of banking services is through the implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning. AI and machine learning can help banks automate many processes that traditionally required human intervention, such as fraud detection and customer service. By automating these processes, banks can reduce the need for manual intervention, which can reduce operational costs. AI and machine learning can also help banks gain insights into customer behavior and preferences, which can enable banks to create more personalized products and services for customers. This can reduce fees and charges for customers by providing them with tailored products and services that they actually need.

Lastly, banking innovation can also reduce the cost of banking services by enabling customers to access financial services through their mobile devices. This can eliminate the need for customers to physically visit a bank branch, which can be costly for banks to maintain. Through mobile banking apps, customers can access a wide range of financial services, such as opening accounts, applying for

loans, and conducting transactions. This reduces the need for physical infrastructure, which can reduce operational costs for banks, thereby leading to lower fees and charges for customers.

In conclusion, banking innovation has the potential to significantly reduce the cost of banking services in Mogadishu, ultimately leading to lower fees and charges for customers. By automating processes, reducing the need for physical infrastructure, and enabling customers to access financial services remotely, banks can significantly reduce operational costs and pass on these savings to customers.

The respondents were asked that **Banking innovation can improve the quality of banking services by providing more convenient and accessible services, such as mobile banking and online banking. This can result in a better customer experience and increased customer satisfaction.**

The Most of respondents of this study 24 (48%) were agree and 4 (8%) Were Strongly disagree,

Mobile banking is an exceptional banking innovation that allows customers to conduct banking transactions anywhere, anytime. Customers can perform a wide range of banking transactions through mobile banking, including account opening, money transfer, bill payments, and balance inquiries. This enhances customer experience as it allows them to conduct transactions from the comfort of their homes or offices at their convenience. This level of convenience not only saves time but also makes banking more accessible to customers without them having to physically visit the bank. Ultimately, this can increase customer satisfaction, as customers feel empowered and have more control over their banking activities.

Online banking is another innovative banking solution that provides customers with easy access to their bank accounts, allowing them to perform transactions and access key banking services through the internet. This enhances customer experience as it provides fast, efficient, and convenient banking services. Online banking makes it possible for customers to check their bank account balances, pay bills, transfer money, and even apply for loans without physically visiting the bank. This service is accessible 24/7, allowing customers to perform transactions even outside normal business hours. This

innovative banking solution ultimately provides more options and enhances the overall customer experience and satisfaction.

Another way that banking innovation can improve the quality of banking services is by providing more personalized and tailored services. With enhanced data analysis capabilities, banks can create more targeted financial products and services that meet specific customer needs. By designing products and services that cater to individual customer profiles and preferences, banks can increase their relevance to customers, thereby improving the overall customer experience. For example, banks can provide more personalized credit cards that cater to different customer demographics, such as those who travel frequently or those who purchase fuel frequently. This personalization creates a more customer-centric approach that ultimately leads to higher customer satisfaction.

In conclusion, banking innovation continues to transform the banking industry and has immense potential to improve the quality of banking services. By providing customers with convenient and accessible services such as mobile and online banking, and creating personalized services that cater to individual needs and preferences, banks can enhance their customer experience and ultimately increase customer satisfaction.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study has provided valuable insights into the impact of banking innovations on the financial performance of banks in Mogadishu, Somalia. The findings indicate that banking innovations have a significant positive impact on the financial performance of banks in terms of profitability, liquidity, and asset quality. The study also highlights the importance of technology adoption and innovation in enhancing the competitiveness of banks in the highly dynamic and competitive banking industry.

The study has also identified some challenges facing banks in Mogadishu, Somalia, such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of skilled human resources, and limited access to funding. These challenges need

to be addressed to enable banks to fully leverage the benefits of banking innovations and enhance their financial performance.

Overall, the study provides important insights for policymakers, regulators, and practitioners in the banking industry in Mogadishu, Somalia, and other developing countries. The findings suggest that there is a need for continued investment in technology and innovation to enhance the competitiveness of banks and promote financial inclusion.

Recommendation:

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that policymakers and regulators in Mogadishu, Somalia, and other developing countries prioritize investment in infrastructure, human resources development, and funding to enable banks to fully leverage the benefits of banking innovations. Additionally, banks should focus on adopting new technologies and innovative practices to enhance their competitiveness and promote financial inclusion. This study can serve as a valuable resource for those interested in understanding the impact of banking innovations on the financial performance of banks in developing countries. Therefore, it is recommended for policymakers, regulators, and practitioners in the banking industry to read this book to gain a better understanding of the importance of technology adoption and innovation in enhancing the competitiveness of banks.

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